

FIXING THE FIXABLE: WHO POINT PREVALENCE SURVEY ON ANTIMICROBIAL USE AT TWIN HOSPITALS OF RAWALPINDI - PAVING THE WAY FOR ANTIMICROBIAL STEWARDSHIP

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Abstract

Objective: To determine the prevalence of antimicrobials and antimicrobial stewardship practices

Study Design: Descriptive Hospital-Based Survey

Place and Duration of Study: Pak Emirates Military Hospital and Combined Military Hospital Rawalpindi, from Feb – May 2025

Methodology: According to World Health Organisation Point Prevalence Survey, only acute care in-patients who were administered antimicrobials were included in the study. Core variables about antibiotic indication and antibiotic usage were recorded. Antibiotics for prophylaxis and treatment, including special cases, were selected depending upon the Anatomical Therapeutic Chemical Classification/Defined Daily Doses system developed by the World Health Organisation. Data were collected using the WHO point prevalence survey Performa.

Results: A total of 670 patients were included in the study, with a gender distribution of 68.5% males and 31.04% females. A total of 52.98% of patients were transferred from the emergency room to the selected ward. A total of 27.61% of the patients were using antibiotics before admission. Of those coming from the emergency department, 13.73% received antibiotics in the emergency department. The study's main findings included 12.51% inappropriateness in unit dose administration, 18.11% in frequency, and 12.61% inappropriateness in antibiotic choice.

Conclusion: The study concludes that there was 12.51% inappropriateness in unit dose administration, 18.11% in frequency, and 12.61% inappropriateness in antibiotic choice.

INTRODUCTION

Before the discovery of antibiotics in the early 20th century, even minor infections were often fatal for patients. This discovery was a game changer in health

care as well as patient prognosis. However, the human race took this for granted. Antimicrobial overuse is one of the world's most significant public health issues.

Antimicrobials developed to kill infectious agents are often ineffective due to the ability of organisms to adapt to that chemical agent. Antimicrobial-resistant organism-contaminated individuals are more likely to need longer, more expensive hospital stays and to die from their infection. A coordinated approach known as "antimicrobial stewardship" encourages the appropriate use of antibiotics and other antimicrobials, improves patient health, lowers microbial resistance, and delays the spread of illnesses that are resistant to multiple drugs.¹

Globally, antibiotic resistance is at unprecedented levels. Globally, new resistance mechanisms are developing and proliferating, endangering our capacity to eradicate common infectious diseases. A growing number of infections, such as TB, blood poisoning, gonorrhoea, pneumonia, and foodborne illnesses, are become harder, if not impossible, to cure as antibiotics lose their effectiveness.² Many authors report worldwide resistance. A systematic review in Bangladesh found a substantial incidence of antibiotic resistance, as well as significant discrepancies in surveillance and information gaps in the methodological data of the studies, including susceptibility testing methods, standards for susceptibility interpretation, and the cause of infection. That study recommended suitable efforts to track and regulate antibiotic use, as well as nationwide surveillance using standardised methodologies, based on the results obtained.³

Ciprofloxacin resistance rates among *Klebsiella pneumoniae* and *Escherichia coli* isolates, as reported to the Global Antimicrobial Resistance and Use Surveillance System (GLASS), exhibited considerable variability, ranging from 4.1% to 79.4% and 8.4% to 92.9%, respectively. In 2019, GLASS collected antimicrobial resistance (AMR) surveillance data from 49 countries on *E. coli*-associated bloodstream infections and from 25 nations, regions, and territories on methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) infections. The median resistance rates for third-generation cephalosporin-resistant *E. coli* and MRSA were 36.0% and 12.11%, respectively; however, these findings lack full national representativeness. Management and control of gonorrhoea have been put at risk due to widespread resistance in different types of *N. gonorrhoeae*. Antibiotic resistance to

other families has quickly developed. Most countries still use ceftriaxone, an injectable extended-spectrum cephalosporin, as an empirical monotherapy for gonorrhoea.⁴

Antimicrobials are the most frequently employed and misused substances, and the consequences of their widespread use have led to the increased emergence of antibiotic-resistant pathogens, necessitating the development of new drugs.^{5,6} In addition to single-agent resistance, multidrug-resistant and extensively drug-resistant (XDR) species prevail in Pakistan, such as XDR-*Salmonella* Typhi and XDR-Tuberculosis (bacteria causing typhoid and tuberculosis, respectively).^{7,8} A retrospective report in 2020 showed a 64% prevalence (in 2017) and 21% prevalence (in 2018) of emerging multidrug-resistant *Salmonella* species, as well as a 25% prevalence (in 2017) and 71% prevalence (in 2018) of XDR-*Salmonella* species in a tertiary care hospital in Karachi. Reports have interpreted that the rise and spread of XDR *S. Typhi* strains with high levels of resistance (25-65% XDR/MDR strains) is quite alarming due to the few treatment options available. This situation necessitates immediate effective preventive measures such as better sanitation, water and food safety, community awareness sessions, and typhoid vaccination campaigns.⁹ A high prevalence of MTB drug resistance in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa was discovered in 2020. Among 34% of presumptive tuberculosis (TB) cases analysed for drug resistance, 4.90% were identified as multidrug-resistant TB (MDR-TB). Streptomycin resistance was the most prevalent (9.0% of isolates), followed by isoniazid resistance (6.0%). In contrast, pyrazinamide resistance was the least common (3.0%). Notably, MDR-TB prevalence rose to 10.4% among patients with prior anti-TB treatment history. These findings underscore the need for a comprehensive, large-scale drug resistance survey to evaluate resistance patterns and enhance TB management strategies.¹⁰ In addition to these two species, *Campylobacter* spp., *Shigella* species, *K. pneumoniae*, and *E. coli* have been found to be multidrug-resistant in various areas of Pakistan.^{11,12,13}

In order to examine the effects of antimicrobial stewardship programs (ASPs), the new field of antimicrobial stewardship finds it difficult to strike a suitable balance between relevant and practical

measures. Antimicrobial use is mostly determined by ASP metrics, even though clinical outcomes and microbiological resistance are crucial indicators of an ASP's impact on a hospital and its patients. Most antimicrobial metrics in use centre on specified daily dosages, therapy days, and expenses, which are typically standardised per 1,000 patient days. Each statistic has a unique combination of benefits and drawbacks and provides somewhat different information. A developing technique for identifying consumption that is reproducible and does not solely rely on complex electronic information systems is point prevalence monitoring of antimicrobial use. Antimicrobial stewardship initiatives are primarily driven by the escalating challenge of antimicrobial resistance (AMR), positioning resistance rates as a critical metric for evaluating the efficacy of Antimicrobial Stewardship Programs (ASPs). ASPs represent an evidence-based strategy to optimise the appropriate utilisation of empiric antibiotic therapy. In a collaborative policy statement, prominent professional societies—including the Infectious Diseases Society of America (IDSA), the Society for Healthcare Epidemiology of America (SHEA), and the Paediatric Infectious Diseases Society (PIDS)—have established core objectives for antimicrobial stewardship. These objectives aim to enhance clinical outcomes associated with antibiotic use while mitigating the selective pressure on bacterial populations that promotes the emergence of resistant strains. A fundamental aspect of ASPs is developing guidelines for empiric antibiotic treatment for common infections.¹⁴

With the emergence of resistance to various antimicrobials, including XDR Salmonella Typhi and XDR Tuberculosis, it is essential to highlight the issue of antimicrobial resistance, the judicious use of antibiotics, and the implementation of antimicrobial stewardship programs at the national level. Various measures must be taken by the authorities, especially in developing countries, such as prohibiting the over-the-counter purchase of antibiotics, updating antibiograms, increasing patient awareness, and implementing strict guidelines by revising care policies

METHODOLOGY

This descriptive hospital-based survey was conducted for the duration of 3.5 months (1st Feb - 15th May 2023) in tertiary care hospitals, Pak Emirates Military Hospital Rawalpindi and Combined Military Hospital Rawalpindi. The survey was approved by the institutional IRB of Pak Emirates Military Hospital (PEMH) and Combined Military Hospital Rawalpindi. After asking for permission from the institutes, the ethical values of patients were kept in mind, and an informed written consent in both English and Urdu was obtained from the patients. Inclusion Criteria: According to the inclusion criteria of the World Health Organisation Point Prevalence Survey, only acute care in-patients who were administered antimicrobials through oral, parenteral, rectal or inhalation routes were included in the study. Patients from both genders, male and female, ≥ 18 years of age were included.

Exclusion Criteria: Patients who were not admitted to inpatient wards at the time of the survey, such as outpatients and emergency department patients who had not been formally admitted. Additionally, patients who were admitted and discharged on the same day were also excluded. Furthermore, individuals whose medical records lacked sufficient clinical or antimicrobial prescription data were excluded from analysis.

A day-to-day survey was conducted in defined hospitals by the investigating team of 5 members under the supervision of the hospital coordinator. The five members were trained for data collection, and one hospital coordinator was in charge of survey conduct and data recording. Antibiotics for prophylaxis and treatment, including special cases, were selected depending upon the Anatomical Therapeutic Chemical Classification/Defined Daily Doses (ATC/DDD) system developed by the World Health Organisation.¹⁶ Data was collected using the WHO point prevalence survey Proforma. A hospital management system (HMS) was used for patient anonymity and selection. One ward was selected as per pre-planned schedules, and data were collected from the patients. Every 1 of 3 patients was selected as the sample of the study. Patient profiles were examined. Core variables about antibiotic indication and antibiotics themselves were recorded.

All the data were coded and analysed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 15.0. Frequency and percentages were calculated for qualitative variables

RESULTS

A total of six hundred and seventy (n=670) patients were included in the study, with a gender distribution of 462 (68.5%) males and 205 (31.04%) females as shown in Table-I. The study design was simple descriptive in nature, so descriptive analysis was performed, and results were generated.

Table-I: Baseline demographic details of patients (n=670)

Variables	Descriptive Statistics	
Age, years		39.5 ±22
Gender, n(%)		
Males	462	68.50%
Females	208	31.04%
Admission Type		
Emergency room	355	52.98%
Elective admission	297	44.32%
Unknown	18	2.68%
Admitting Ward		
General ward	489	72.98%
High Dependency Unit - HDU	102	15.22%
Medical ICU - MICU	21	3.13%
Surgical ICU - SICU	17	3.73%
Coronary Care Unit - CCU	16	2.38%
Unknown	16	2.38%
Admitting Services		
Orthopaedics	39	5.82%
Urology	46	6.86%
General Surgery	135	20.14%
Cardiology	56	8.35%
Internal Medicine	254	37.91%
Infectious Diseases	18	2.68%
Gastroenterology	14	2.08%
Ear, Nose, Throat (E.N.T.)	14	2.08%
Nephrology	26	3.88%
Pulmonology	32	4.77%
Haematology	12	1.79%
Plastic Surgery	7	1.04%
Unknown	10	1.49%
Febrile At Admission		
Yes	113	16.86%
Indoor Treatment in Healthcare Facility in Past 90 Days		
No	442	65.97%
Yes	142	21.19%
Unknown	86	12.83%

Table-II presents the clinical details of patients who were administered antibiotics in an emergency situation, and details of the catheter and intubation. The majority of the patients received peripheral venous and urinary catheters.

Table-II: Clinical Details of The Patients (n=670)

Antibiotics Administered in ER (n=375)		
No	263	39.25%
Yes	92	13.73%
Not applicable (not admitted through ER)	315	47.01%
Central Venous Catheter During Admission (n=670)		
No	542	80.89%
Yes	118	17.61%
Unknown	10	1.49%
Peripheral Venous Catheter During Admission (n=670)		
Yes	658	98.20%
No	12	1.79%
Urinary Catheter During Admission (n=670)		
No	286	42.68%
Yes	360	53.73%
Unknown	24	3.58%
Intubation During Admission (n=89)		
Yes	89	13.28%
Critical Care Bay Detention (n=44)		
Yes	44	6.56%
TLC Count on Admission		12876±4584
Fever Within 24hours of Admission		184 27.46%
Allergy (Hypersensitivity) History		
No	465	69.40%
Yes	87	12.98%
Unknown	85	17.61%

TLC: total leucocyte count; ER: emergency room; HC: healthcare

Table-III presents patterns of antimicrobial use. The majority of the patients were receiving antibacterial therapy during their hospital stay. A good thing found was that more than 60% of the patients received a culture check facility, and a relevant culture was taken before starting their antibiotic therapy. The point prevalence of antibiotic use was 72.6%.

Table-III: Anti-microbials patterns and usage (n=670)

Usage During Hospital Stay		
Anti-bacterial drugs	582	86.86%
Anti-malarial drugs	85	12.68%
Anti-fungal drugs	37	5.52%
Documented Reason for Antibiotic Administration (n=486)		
Surgical Prophylaxis	181	32.78%
Community-associated infections - CAI	176	31.88%

Healthcare-associated infections - HAI	102	73.53%
Medical Prophylaxis	85	15.39%
Other	8	1.44%
For Surgical Prophylaxis: Treatment Duration (n=181)		
One dose	36	19.88%
Multiple doses on one day	55	30.38%
Multiple doses on more than one day	90	49.72%
Extended Surgical Prophylaxis: Duration (n=98)		
Minimum-maximum days	1-18	
Median (IQR) days	2.0(1.0-5.0)	
Surgical Prophylaxis: Systems (n=181)		
Urinary tract	39	21.54%
Gastrointestinal	52	28.72%
Cardiovascular	26	14.36%
Skin, soft tissue, joints and bone	38	20.99%
Otolaryngology	15	8.28%
Unknown	11	6.07%
HAI/CAI Site of Infection (n=139)		
Infections of the CNS	12	4.31%
Pneumonia	39	14.02%
Intra-abdominal sepsis, including the hepatobiliary region	36	12.94%
Symptomatic lower UTI (e.g., cystitis)	28	10.07%
Gastrointestinal infections	10	5.03%
Surgical infection involving skin or soft tissue, excluding bone	18	6.47%
Infections of the ear, nose, throat, larynx, and mouth	8	2.87%
Surgical site infection involving skin or soft tissue but not bone	14	5.03%
Clinical sepsis	21	7.55%
Non-surgical osteomyelitis, osteoarthritis	19	6.83%
Septic arthritis and osteomyelitis of the surgical site		
Completely undefined site, with no systemic inflammation	8	2.87%
Symptomatic upper urinary tract infections (e.g., pyelonephritis)	12	4.31%
Asymptomatic bacteriuria	9	3.23%
Laboratory-confirmed bacteraemia	15	5.39%
Febrile neutropenia or other forms of manifestation of infection in an immunocompromised host	13	4.67%
Systemic inflammatory response with no clear anatomical site	11	3.95%
Missing	1	0.35%
Culture Before Antibiotics Administration (n=552)		
Yes	339	61.41%
No	110	19.92%
Not applicable (e.g., used as prophylaxis)	48	8.69%
Partially	38	6.88%
Unknown	17	3.07%
Antibiotics Used (n=552)		

Amoxicillin / Clavulanic acid	75	13.58%
Amikacin	8	1.44%
Azithromycin	21	3.80%
Benzathine benzyl penicillin	7	1.26%
Cefazolin	8	1.44%
Cefoparazone / sulbactam	11	1.99%
Ceftazidime	36	6.52%
Ciprofloxacin	30	5.43%
Ceftriaxone	93	16.84%
Clarithromycin	13	2.35%
Cefuroxime	19	3.44%
Clindamycin	2	0.31%
Colistin	6	1.08%
Ertapenem	1	0.18%
Fosfomycin (oral)	11	1.99%
Levofloxacin	9	1.63%
Meropenem	86	15.57%
Metronidazole	29	5.25%
Piperacillin/tazobactam	32	5.79%
Rifaximin	16	2.89%
Sulfamethoxazole /trimethoprim	6	1.08%
Tigecycline	4	0.72%
Vancomycin	21	3.80%
Other*	8	1.44%
Route of Administration (n=552)		
Oral	128	23.18%
Parenteral	424	76.81%
Route of Administration: Parenteral		
Intramuscular	5	1.17%
Intravenous intermittent	355	83.72%
Intravenous continuous infusion	3	0.70%
Other	37	8.72%
Unknown	24	5.66%
Route of Administration: Parenteral to Oral Switch (n=424)		
Yes	311	73.34%
No	113	26.65%
Unknown	0	
Missing Doses (n=12)		
Treatment Purpose (n=552)		
Directed	108	19.56%
Prophylaxis (surgical=medical)	226	48.18%
Empiric	178	32.24%

Table-IV presents the need for stewardship in twin hospitals. Some reasons were noted for the need for AS, such as noncompliance (10.76%), unnecessary antibiotic prescriptions at the time of discharge (6.46%), extended surgical prophylaxis (20%), and incorrect dose (8.92%).

Table-IV: Antimicrobial stewardship

Antimicrobial stewardship	Descriptive Statistics	
Applicable	262	47.46%
Non-applicable	226	40.94%
Missing	64	11.59%
Antimicrobial Stewardship: Reasons		
Unjustified prolonged duration of therapy	65	20%
Antibiotic not indicated	28	8.61%
Violation of surgical prophylaxis guidelines	35	10.76%
Inappropriate choice of antibiotics	41	12.61%
Extended surgical prophylaxis	11	3.38%
Overlapping spectrum	34	10.34%
Incorrect dose	29	8.92%
Unnecessary antibiotics on discharge	21	6.46%
Used an antimicrobial against its resistant microorganism	18	5.53%
Narrow-spectrum options are available	19	5.84%
Restricted antibiotics use	8	2.46%
Clinical contraindications for existing antibiotics	9	2.76%
Other	7	2.15%

While finding the biological data most blood and urine samples were taken as specimen types (Table-V), and more than 50% of the culture specimens were found to be positive after culture testing. Resistant species, found in the majority, were *carbapenem-resistant gram-negative rods* (33.33%) and *third-generation cephalosporin-resistant gram-negative rods* (21.87%).

Table-V: Data from Microbiological Perspective

Type of Specimen (n=477)	Descriptive Statistics	
Blood	228	47.79%
Urine	116	24.31%
Sputum/respiratory sample	35	7.33%
Wound	29	6.07%
Sterile fluids	44	9.22%
Other	25	5.24%
Culture Results (n=549)		
CS not sent	53	21.54%
Positive	131	53.25%
Negative	62	25.20%
Phenotypes as Per Resistance (n=92)		
Carbapenem-resistant gram-negative rod	32	33.33%
Vancomycin-resistant enterococcus	16	16.66%
Third-generation cephalosporin-resistant gram-negative rod	21	21.87%

Methicillin-Resistant Staphylococcus Aureus	11	11.45%
Not resistant	16	16.66%

The inpatient mortality rate (Table-VI) was found to be 6.26%. The median days of therapy (DOT) per agent was 7 (6.0–8.0) days.

Table-VI: Outcome

Patient Outcomes	Descriptive Statistics	
Survivors	597	89.10%
Non-survivors	42	6.26%
Unknown	31	4.62%
Antimicrobials for Outdoor		
Yes	501	74.77%
DOT Per Antibacterial (n=480)		
Median (IQR) days	3 (2.0-4.0)	
Minimum-maximum days	1-21	
Antimicrobials Per Patient		
Median (IQR)	1(1-1)	
Minimum-maximum	1-4	

DOT: Days of therapy

DISCUSSION

The present survey gathered data regarding antibiotic prescribing practices and other details pertinent to the treatment and management of infectious diseases in hospitalised patients, and complemented antimicrobial consumption surveillance in twin hospitals of Rawalpindi. In our study, 27.61% of the patients were using antibiotics before admission, which is less than the 52% prevalence reported in 2016.¹⁷

Antibiotic usage in Pakistan rose by 65% between 2000 and 2015, and even in 2015, Pakistan was among the countries showing the highest consumption of antibiotics along with China and India, so the present results showed an improvement in self-medication of antibiotics in our region.¹⁸

Emergency departments (EDs) indicate an especially significant setting for tackling inappropriate antimicrobial prescribing practices, given the regular administration of antimicrobial agents in an environment that lies at the interface of the community and the hospital. The present survey showed that 47% of the patients admitted to wards did not come from the emergency department, but only 13.73% of those coming from the emergency department received antibiotics in the emergency

department. Antibiotic use has been reported to be 25–63% inappropriate and unnecessary in office-based practitioners.¹⁹ Previously, a 9% prevalence of antibiotic use was found in Denmark in 2010.²⁰

Appropriate unit dose, frequency and choice of antimicrobial agent are important factors that can prevent resistance, morbidity and mortality. Our study found 12.51% inappropriateness in unit dose administration, 18.11% in frequency and 12.61% inappropriateness in choice of antibiotics. A 2019 longitudinal study conducted in Lahore, Pakistan, revealed elevated rates of inappropriate antibiotic utilisation among hospitalised patients. The investigation, which evaluated 1,185 patients receiving 2,022 antimicrobial prescriptions, found that 70.3% of participants had at least one inappropriately prescribed antibiotic. Respiratory tract infections accounted for 27.2% of cases, with 62.8% of these patients receiving non-optimal therapy.²¹ The analysis demonstrated significant variability in inappropriate prescribing across antimicrobial classes: carbapenems (70.9%), macrolides (74.6%), other antibacterials (73.1%), fluoroquinolones (64.2%), and aminoglycosides (35.8%).

Inappropriate use of antibiotics seems to be widespread around the world, contributing to the evolution of resistant organisms. Compared to the present study, a previous point-prevalence study in a Vietnamese hospital revealed that n=5,104 of n=7,571 patients (67.4%) were on antibiotics.²² Analysis of antibiotic prescribing patterns across hospital departments revealed significant variation, with the highest prescription rates in surgical wards (93.2%) and the lowest in medical wards (48.2%). Among 5,104 evaluated patients, cephalosporins (70.2%), penicillin (21.6%), and aminoglycosides (18.9%) comprised the most frequently administered antibiotic classes. Clinical audit data demonstrated that 30.8% of cases (1,573/5,104) lacked appropriate prescription indications. Multivariate analysis identified national hospitals, obstetrics/gynaecology departments, and surgical wards as significant risk factors for inappropriate antibiotic prescribing. These findings align with prior research documenting excessive cephalosporin use, where 67.2% of prescriptions were clinically unjustified. Penicillins were administered to n=283 patients, with 71.0% being prescribed for the incorrect indication, dosage, or both.²¹

A hospital survey in the United States reported that 576 of 1941 antibiotic therapy days were unneeded due to excessive prescribing, consumption of antibiotics for nonbacterial purposes, and treatment with colonising agents.²³ In Romania, 49.2% of prescribed antibiotics in a hospital were inappropriate due to erroneous dosages, length of time, and indications.²⁴

In the United States, the Centers for Disease Control (CDC) reported that 55.7% of patients in 323 healthcare facilities received antibiotics throughout their hospital stay.²⁵ The misuse of antimicrobials is also high in hospitals in low and middle-income countries (LMICs), which is exacerbated in some countries by high rates of HIV, tuberculosis, and malaria among inpatients.^{26,27,28} Multiple studies conducted in Pakistan have demonstrated persistent inappropriate antibiotic prescribing practices in hospital settings, notwithstanding antimicrobial stewardship program (ASP) implementation efforts. These investigations revealed limited physician awareness of existing ASP

initiatives, suggesting substantial gaps between policy implementation and clinical adoption.^{29,32}

In 2016, the Medical Microbiology and Infectious Diseases Society of Pakistan (MMIDSP) formally adopted the World Health Organisation's (WHO) Global Action Plan on Antimicrobial Resistance, implementing hospital-based antibiotic stewardship programs (ASPs) as part of its strategic response to the growing antimicrobial resistance (AMR) crisis.^{33,34,35} Implementation of antimicrobial stewardship programs (ASPs) remains inadequate across Pakistani healthcare facilities, reflecting a broader pattern in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs) where ASP adoption lags behind high-income nations.^{35,36} The present study found that ASP is needed in current hospitals due to unjustified prolonged duration of therapy (20%), non-compliance with surgical prophylaxis guidelines (10.76%), unnecessary antibiotic prescriptions at the time of patient discharge (6.46%), inappropriate choice of antibiotics (12.61%), incorrect dose (8.92%), and overlapping antibiotic spectrum (10.34%).

LIMITATION

We only included two health setups in the study; further studies should be done to include data from twin cities, to assess stewardship in all hospitals (private and government), so that comparisons can be made on how private setups differ in terms of implementing antibiotic stewardship in their healthcare setups.

CONCLUSION

This study concludes that antimicrobial stewardship is required in selected hospitals, due to the increased trend of empiric therapy, unjustified prolonged duration of treatment, noncompliance with surgical prophylaxis guidelines, unnecessary antibiotic prescriptions at the time of patient discharge, inappropriate choice of antibiotics, and overlapping antibiotic spectrum. ID consultation is an important factor that is missed in the majority of cases in both hospitals.

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RA & SS: Conception and study design, Data Acquisition, Manuscript writing, Analysis & interpretation, Final approval

SN & MK: Concept and study design, Analysis & interpretation, critical review & final approval.

TK & SF: Concept and study design, Analysis & interpretation, critical review & final approval.

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